

A Guide for Teaching Business Management in Senior High Schools – Case Study at Bompeh Senior High Technical School

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DEPARTMENT OF INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES

COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION-KUMASI
DEPARTMENT OF INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES

POST GRADUATE DIPLOMA IN EDUCATION

AKENTEN APPIAH-MENKA UNIVERSITY OF SKILLS TRAINING AND ENTREPRENEURIAL
DEVELOPMENT

COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION-KUMASI
DEPARTMENT OF INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES

POST GRADUATE IN DIPLOMA IN EDUCATION
A GUIDE FOR TEACHING BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS

BY
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A PROJECT WORK SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES,
AKENTEN APPIAH-MENKA UNIVERSITY OF SKILLS TRAINING AND ENTREPRENEURIAL
DEVELOPMENT –KUMASIIN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF POST GRADUATE DIPLOMA IN EDUCATION

AUGUST, 2021

DECLARATION

CANDIDATE’S DECLARATION

I hereby declare that, is the result of my original work and that no part of it has been presented to another in the institution or elsewhere.

Candidate’s Name.....
Signature:
Date

SUPERVISOR’S DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the preparation and presentation of this project work was supervised in accordance with the guidelines on supervision of project work laid down by the Akenten Appiah-Menka University of Skills Training and Entrepreneurial Development (Previously UEW-K)

Supervisor’s Name
Signature:
Date

DEDICATION

To my mother Mrs. Rose Esther Essel whom I see as an inspiration in every step that I take. You have always been there for me even when no one is supporting me .And all my course mate during the program

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank the Almighty God for given me the ability to think, the inspiration and strength given me throughout the project work. Glory be unto His name. I also wish to express my sincere gratitude to my project supervisor, Dr. Philip Oti Agyen .And to all my lecturers at Akenten Appiah-Menka University of Skills Training and Entrepreneurial Development–Kumasi (Previously UEW-K) . I cannot forget all the teachers at Bompeh Senior High Technical School – Takoradi, especially to the Head of business Department, Madam Gloria Ansah for their love and guidance exhibited towards me during my teaching practice.

Finally, to my Parent and Siblings (Simons -Dadzie family) God bless you all.

ABSTRACT

The research seek examine and assess teachers guide in delivering business Management at Senior High School. Certain contributing factors is the nature of contributed effectiveness, efficiencies and quality of teaching were examined and recommendations for progress and create opportunity for more study for improvement.

Chapter one focuses on teaching syllabus for year two which covers three terms with sample teaching syllabus.

Chapter two examines lesson order and scheme of work which takes into consideration sample for three terms.

Chapter three is the presentation of lesson plan for four topics for effective teaching and learning.

Chapter four is the teaching and learning resources which include instructional sheets which consider in-depth information for the pupils.

Chapter five is about the test items construction, a table of specification, test items (objectives and essay) and marking scheme. The last chapter focuses on the summary, conclusion and recommendation of the whole study.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

A. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

In the Ghana structuring of the educational procedures that was aimed towards strengthen and acquire vocational and entrepreneurial capabilities in all educational level.

The low level of basic managerial and business mind set of graduate produced in the secondary cycle of educational system demanded the need to integrate various subjects including financial accounting, economic, cost accounting and business management under business studies in the new era of educational structuring and reforming.

Business management deals with how individuals and organization coordinate, plan the activism and resource through implementation of appropriate strategies to achieve an organizational goals and objectives. The subject aid students with knowledge about managerial and effective utilization of resource to achieve targeted goal.

This study was conducted at Bompeh Senior High Technical School in the Sekondi-Takoradi District of the Western Region. The school has a total student population size of two thousand five hundred sixty six (2566) students of which Thousand six hundred and six (1066) are Green track and Thousand five hundred (1500) are Gold track and teaching staff of Hundreds of twenty five (125).

B. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Business Management is an integration of several subjects such as Economics, Accounting, Costing and business education. It is not very difficult to get teachers who are versatile enough to teach the combination of several subject areas effectively. But it is rare to find competent teachers who possess adequate knowledge of all the necessary areas, many teachers of Business management rather concentrate on the subject areas which they are Comfortable with and neglect the others. Students also tend to be selective and abandon areas which they have little interest in or perceive as difficult. This leads to ineffective teaching and learning of the subject from students hence making schools not to achieve their academic desire and goals in the course.

C. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to prepare a guide which will enhance the teaching of Business Management in Senior High Schools in Ghana. The guide will outline the necessary teaching and learning resources to use, preparations to make and procedures to follow to achieve effective teaching and learning of the subject.

D. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study would help teachers to make adequate preparation especially in areas where they do not have expert knowledge before undertaking a lesson. This would assist effective delivery of Business Management lessons in our schools.

Moreover, the study would benefit educationists, policy-makers and other stakeholders in their decisions and policies regarding to the advancement of Senior High School Education. Again, it is aimed that educationists and administrators in areas with similar situations would find the conclusions and recommendations of this project essential to their own conditions.

Finally, the study would contribute to the in depth much Literature relating to teaching of Business Management in High Schools and ascertain future researchers on related course of study.

E. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This work is limited to the teaching of business management in senior high of Green track of Bompeh senior high technical school, Takoradi as well as the teaching syllabus, lesson order, lesson plan and scheme of work. It covered the period of second term of the 2021/2022 academic year.

F. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Most of the time many research undertaking encounter various fundamental limitations and this study was no Exception. A major limitation to this project was the lack of adequate financial resources. The project involves typing, printing and travelling which requires a lot of money. Lack of readily organized data for the study was a limiting factor, however, within the constraints; all attempts were made to undertake a valid comprehensive study.

Again, the difficulty in finding appreciable number of education stakeholders to share their experiences, challenges and the unwillingness of others to share their information to enrich the project.

Finally, The fact that the project is time and labour involving. Typing, editing and getting to various geographical locations to gather information all demand physical efforts and time, but all these are in limited supply.

CHAPTER TWO

TEACHING SYLLABUS, LESSON ORDER AND SCHEME OF WORK

INTROUDUCTION

A. *TEACHING SYLLABUS*

Teaching Syllabus is one of the important material in the teaching and learning process .After rigorously going through this section, it is envisaged that student is will be able to:

- Give reason for preparing and using a syllabus when going to teaching
- Plan a syllabus before and after teaching
- Explain what a syllabus is about
- Prepare a teaching syllabus

a) INTRODUCTION

A syllabus is a document that takes into account of a course of study, which are mostly not detailed and in -depth, it is generally aids as a guide to teachers and it is required of a teaching to re-arrange them for an effective and efficient instruction and learning procedures.

b) Reason for having a syllabus

The rational for having and using a syllabus are sum up as below:

- It aids the instructor/teacher to study and plan his work over a specific given period of the course.
- It help the teacher to ascertain the performance of the students to a set standard.
- It the concepts to be developed and gives information to the teacher on what the pupils should learn.
- It enables the teacher to know at a glance the topics to be covered and to be treated
- It ensures standardization of the same course held at different learning areas.

B. *CONTENT OF SYLLABUS*

A well prepared syllabus should consist of the following main sections:

- Preamble / instruction: this part contains statements that express the reasons for providing the course and how it fits into the curriculum of a particular programme.
- Objective: behavioral objectives to be achieved for studying the course
- Entry requirements: who qualify to enroll on the course? These should be clearly stated.
- Duration: these specify the length of time allocated for studying the course.
- Assessment method: Guidelines should be given on the methods for assessing students that is (40% continues assessment and 60% end of term examination)
- Topics: all lists of relevant areas of coverage should be included
- Major activities: the activities teachers and students are to perform are included.
- Instructional materials: the activities teachers and students are to perform are included.
- Instructional materials: these material include; textbooks, equipment, tools, audio-visual resources Eg. (photographs, record players films etc)
- Reference: A list of useful references, to be used by both the teacher and the students.

C. *PLANNING A SYLLABUS*

Syllabus planning and advisory committee constitute the following. The committee is made of:

- Representative of government
- Representative of the examining body. Eg WAEC, Technical Exam unit
- Representative of education.
- Representative form industry and commerce. Eg ECG, AGC

The committee is well denoted by all interest groups to ensure that no groups of individuals are left out. To break down the syllabus, the following information should be critically examined.

- The objectives of the course.
- The content of the syllabus
- The suitable teaching and learning techniques to be used.
- The proper approaches for assessing whether students have understood the lesson

An examination syllabic (often referred to as the traditional syllabus) does not take into consideration the competencies students are to require, appropriate teaching strategies and methods for assessing what the students has been taught. These short comings of the examination syllabus have necessitated the translation of this type of syllabus into a teaching syllabus.

D. *PARTS OF TEACHING SYLLABUS*

A well prepared teaching syllabus follow a certain concepts, namely

- Sections
- General objectives
- Units
- Specific objectives
- Content
- Teaching / Learning activities
- Evaluation

E. *SECTIONS AND UNITS*

Annually work has been divided into unit. A unit which consist of large degree of homogeneous group of knowledge within the subject .The sections are further broken down into units which consists of a core related and more homogeneous body of knowledge and skills. (CRDD 1999).

Every unit of the syllabus has a set of general objectives which describes precisely and accurately what the leaner is require to be able to do in order to define and describe learning. The general objectives are summary of the specific objectives of the various units. Each unit is structured in five columns units, specific objectives contents, teaching and learning activities and evaluation.

- **Unit:** The first column consists of unit which is based on the section depends on how the major topic of the section has broken down. The units are numbered.
- **Specific Objectives:** In this column, the expected learning outcome or the terminal behavior expected of the learners when topics treated are listed logically under each main topic.
- **Content:** The content in third column of the syllabus presents a selected body of information that will be needed to use in teaching a particular topic.
- **Teaching and learning activities:** The most effective and efficient teaching methodology that gears towards maximumpupil's involvement to bring about each of the state terminal behaviors stated in column four.
- **Evaluation:** Suggestions and exercises for evaluation of the lesson of each topic are indicated in column five.

It contains the right means of assessing and examining whether or not the learner can exhibit the expected behavioral ways stated in the specific objective column.

F. FORMAT FOR TEACHING SYLLABUS

NAME : YEAR
INSTITUTION : FORM
DEPARTMENT : SEMESTER
SUBJECT :

G. SAMPLE TEACHING SYLLABUS

NAME: EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE YEAR: 2021
INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECH.SCH CLASS: SHS TWO
DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS SEMESTER: ONE
SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT TITLE: NATURE OF MANAGEMENT

H. GENERAL OBJECTIVES:

By the end of the lesson, the student will be able to:

- appreciate the world of business
- Be aware of the forms of business organizations being operated in Ghana.
- Appreciate the need to study management.
- Recognize the social, ethical and legal responsibilities of business.
- Recognize the need for business to respond to their social, ethical and legal responsibilities.
- Acquire skills in using principles learnt to solve problems through case study.

UNIT	SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	CONTENT	TEACHING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES	EVALUATION
UNIT 1 FORMS OF BUSINESS ORGANIZATION	<p>The student will be able to:</p> <p>1.1.1 Explain the world of business</p> <p>1.1.2 Explain the concept of business organization.</p> <p>1.1.3 Identify the major forms of Business organization and their characteristics.</p>	<p><u>Evolution of man's efforts to supply his/her needs since creation</u> Man has since time immemorial employed several ways in which to supply his needs and wants.</p> <p><u>Concept of business organization</u> Entity involved in the transformation of resources into products and services in order to meet the needs of people.</p> <p><u>Major forms of business organizations</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sole proprietorship, - Partnership, - Limited liability company, - Public corporation, - Co-operatives 	<p>Assist students to:</p> <p>Trace the evolution of business</p> <p>Note: Use graphical presentation in doing this.</p> <p>Discuss the concept of business organization.</p> <p>Note: Stress on the importance of management identity and discuss the characteristics of each form of business organization.</p>	<p>Organize a symposium on the topic.</p> <p>What forms of business organization are more sustainable over time?</p>

UNIT	SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	CONTENT	TEACHING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES	EVALUATION
UNIT 1(CONT'D) FORMS OF BUSINESS ORGANIZATION	<p>The student will be able to;</p> <p>1.1.4 Describe the procedures for the formation of the various business organizations.</p> <p>1.1.5 Outline the advantages and disadvantages of the various forms of business organization.</p> <p>1.1.6 Describe the methods for distribution of profits and absorption of losses in various forms of business organization.</p> <p>1.1.7 Outline the causes of business failure.</p>	<p>Assist students to:</p> <p>Role play the procedures for the formation of various business organizations. Emphasize the documents used for registration.</p> <p>Brainstorm to bring out advantages and disadvantages of the various forms of business organizations.</p> <p>Discuss methods for sharing profits and losses in various business organizations</p> <p>Discuss the reasons why some businesses fail. e.g. managerial incompetence – lack of competent managers for the business enterprise</p>	<p>Write the advantages and disadvantages of partnership.</p> <p>State the advantages and disadvantages of sole proprietorship. Why is it common in Ghana</p> <p>Write an essay on causes of business failure.</p>	<p>Students in groups discuss how they would know the procedures in forming their various business and the possible challenges that can contribute to failures and how to overcome them</p>

• **SAMPLE TEACHING SYLLABUS**

NAME : EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE

INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECH.SCH

DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS

SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

YEAR: 2021

CLASS: SHS TWO

SEMESTER: ONE

TITLE: MEANING AND PROCESS
OF MANAGEMENT

UNIT	SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	CONTENT	TEACHING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES	EVALUATION
UNIT 2 MEANING AND PROCESS OF MANAGEMENT	The student will be able to: 1.2.1 Explain management 1.2.2 Explain the basic functions of management. 1.2.3 Identify the different levels of management. 1.2.4 Identify types of managers by their functions in organizations. 1.2.5 Identify careers in business management.	<u>Meaning of management</u> Involves coordinating and overseeing the work activities of others to achieve organizational goals and objectives through the use of appropriate strategies and tasks <u>The four basic functions of management</u> - planning - organizing - directing - controlling, monitoring, evaluation and feedback <u>Levels of management</u> - Top management/ - Corporate level - Middle management/Functional level - Lower management/operational level <u>Types of Managers</u> - Administration - Finance - Marketing	Assist students to: Brainstorm the meaning of management. Note: stress that management aims at accomplishing goals efficiently and effectively. Discuss why it is necessary to plan, organize, direct and control, monitor, evaluate and the need for feedback on the activities of organizations. Discuss the different levels of management designed in helping to meet corporate objectives. Describe the functions of each of the managers listed under content.	Students in groups discuss how they would set goals and use the process of planning, organizing, directing, monitoring and controlling in their school activities and write report for class forum. What is the relationship between the board of directors and the various levels of management of a company Students interview some managers in their locality and present a report to be discussed in class

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human Resource - Procurement - Production/Operations - etc <p><u>Careers in management</u> e.g. Human Resource Manager, Finance Manager, Accounts Manager, Marketing Manager, Transport Manager, etc.</p>	Discuss careers in management.	
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• **LESSON ORDER AND SCHEME OF WORK**

➤ **INTRODUCTION**

A lesson order helps the teacher to see at a glance the topics to be treated in a particular term or semester .The topic are arranged in a such a manner that the easy topic are taught first before the difficult ones.

➤ **POINTS TO CONSIDER WHEN PLANNING THE LESSON ORDER**

- The number of weeks in a particular term or semester
- The term or semester the lesson order is being planning for the total number of periods allocated to the subject
- Duration of period
- Total numbers of topics
- Class exercises or tests to be given to the student
- Educational visit/filed trips
- The level of the students ability
- The period of revision
- Sporting activities (e.g inter houses, inter colleges)
- End of term examinations
- Buffer periods

• **LESSON ORDER FORMAT**

NAME : CLASS:
 INSTITUTION : SEMESTER:
 DEPARTMENT : YEAR:
 SUBJECT:

LESSON ORDER	WEEK	DATE	DURATION	TOPIC

• **LESSON ORDER**

NAME: EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE. **FORM: TWO**
INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECH, SCH. **SEMESTER: TWO**
DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS **YEAR: 2021**
SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

LESSON ORDER	WEEK	DATE	DURATION	TOPIC
-	17/01/21	1	105mins	GENERAL CLEANING
1	25/02/21	2	105mins	NATURE OF MANAGEMENT
2	1/03/21	3	105mins	NATURE OF MANAGEMENT
3	9/03/21	4	105mins	CLASS TEST
4	15/03/21	5	105mins	MEANING AND PROCESS OF MANAGEMENT
5	23/04/21	6	105mins	MEANING AND PROCESS OF MANAGEMENT
6	1/04/21	7	105mins	ROLE OF GOVERNMENT IN THE ECONOMY
7	8/04/21	8	105mins	CLASS TEST
8	12/04/21	9	105mins	BUFFER PERIOD
9	23/04/21	10	105mins	ROLE OF GOVERNMENT IN THE ECONOMY
10	29/04/21	11	105mins	INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS AND CHALLENGES OF DEVELOPING ECONOMIES
11	5/05/21	12	105mins	INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS AND CHALLENGES OF DEVELOPING ECONOMIES
12	12/05/21	13	105mins	INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS AND CHALLENGES OF DEVELOPING ECONOMIES
13	19/05/21	14	105mins	REVISION
14	25/05/21	15	105mins	EXAMINATION

• **LESSON ORDER**

NAME: EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE.
INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECH, SCH.
DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS
SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

FORM: THREE
SEMESTER: TWO
YEAR: 2021

LESSON ORDER	WEEK	DATE	DURATION	UNIT/TOPIC
-	17/05/21	1	105mins	GENERAL CLEANING
1	24/05/21	2	105mins	GLOBALIZATION AND ECONOMIC INTEGRATION
2	7/06/21	3	105mins	GLOBALIZATION AND ECONOMIC INTEGRATION
3	14/06/21	4	105mins	GLOBALIZATION AND ECONOMIC INTEGRATION
4	14/06/21	5	105mins	CLASS TEST
5	21/06/21	6	105mins	FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF MANAGEMENT I
6	28/06/21	7	105mins	FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF MANAGEMENT I
7	5/07/21	8	105mins	CLASS TEST
8	12/07/21	9	105mins	FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF MANAGEMENT II
9	19/07/21	10	105mins	FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF MANAGEMENT II
10	26/07/21	11	105mins	BUFFER PERIOD
11	2/08/21	12	105mins	ENREPRENUERSHIP AND SMALL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT
12	9/08/21	13	105mins	ENREPRENERSHIP AND SMALL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT
13	16/08/21	14	105mins	REVISION
14	23/08/21	15	105mins	EXAMINATION

• **SCHEME OF WORK**

NAME: EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE.
INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECH, SCH.
DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS
SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

FORM: TWO
SEMESTER: TWO
YEAR: 2021

A scheme of work is a systematic arrangement of a syllabus for teaching and learning purposes.

The scheme of work is more detailed than the lesson order to enable the teacher to know exactly what he or she should do and teacher. A scheme of work is a planned for usage within a specific term or semester. It links all the lesson plans and it shows at a glance the topics to be covered every week and also scheme of work also provides the order and periods during which other activities.

It is planned in a way that if there is change of the teacher, the new teacher can be able to use it when the regular teacher is absent. The factors considered when planning the scheme of work

- The number of weeks in the term
- The duration for each period (in minutes)
- The general objectives or the lesson
- The content objectives of the lesson
- The content (i.e area of coverage)
- The teaching method to be employed
- The relation of the topics to other courses of the programmes

- The relevant instructional material for trenching and learning the individual topic charts, models, real objects and instructional sheet.

3	70	Forms of business organization	Recognize the social, ethical and legal responsibilities of business	Procedures for the formation of various business organization 1. Registration of business name Act 151, 1992 2. Incorporated partnership (Act 152, 1992) 3. Company code (Act 179, 1963)	Discussion	Economics/ Accounting	Explanation and B.Ms text book	ANECA. (2005). Business management and administration degree white book	Prepare a brief note on business Act 151, 1992	
4	70	Forms of business organization	Acquire skills in using principles learnt to solve problems through case study	Outline the advantages and disadvantages of various business forms	Lecture, explanation and discussion	Economics / Accounting	Explanation and B.M text books	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	State and explain 3 advantages of sole proprietorship	
4	35	The legal framework of Business	Understand the legal framework in which business operate	Meaning of legal framework - it is the set of guidelines , rules of conduct and regulations within which business must operate and enforceable in the court	Explanation	Economics	Explanation and B.M note books	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	Mention four rules you think business should operate with.	
5	70	The legal framework of Business	Understand the principles of contract and agency and how these affect business	The element and general principles of contract 1. Offer and acceptance 2. Intention to contract 3. Capacity 4. Formalities 5. Illegality 6. Consideration 7. negotiation	Explanation and discussion	Economics	Explanation	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	Explain four of the principles in your own words	
5	35	The legal framework of Business	Appreciate the importance of negotiation instrument in business	Classification of contract 1. Simple 2. Specialty 3. Contract of record	Lecture, explanation and discussion	Economics/ labour relation books	Explanation	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	State and explain the classifications of contract	
6	70	The legal framework of business	Develop the skills acquired in solving basic problems through case study	Ways of discharging a contract 1. Performance 2. Agreement 3. Frustration 4. Breach 5. Lapse of time 6. Act of God or nature	Explanation and discussion	Labour relation books	Explanation	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	Explain various ways of discharging contract	
6	35	Financial and Non-bank financial institution	Understand the role of Financial and non-bank institution in business	Financial institution- An institution which provides financial services like banking , savings, insurance etc	Explanation, Discussion	Economic /Accounting books	Explanations	DD (2007) Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)	Give five financial sector you know	

7	35	C L A S S T E S T								
7	70	B U F F E R P E R I O D								
8	70	Financial	Be aware of the	Meaning of money-	Explanation	Economic/Accou	Adentwi, K.I,	State 5		

		and Non-bank financial institution	relationship between money, banking, inflation and deflation	Any commodity which is generally accepted as a means of payment and settlement of debt		Accounting books	Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Educational	countries and their currency	
8	35	Financial and Non-bank financial institution	Recognize the role of the stock exchange and insurance in business	The function of the central bank 1. Issuing and redemption currency 2. Banker to the government 3. Banker to other banks 4. Lender of last resort 5. Control money supply	Discussion and Explanation	Economic/Accounting books	Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Educational	State three functions of the central bank in sustainability of consolidated banks in Ghana.	

9	70	Financial and Non-bank financial institution	Develop skills in solving basic business problems through case study	Types of account 1. Savings 2. Current 3. Fixed deposit 4. Call account	Explanation and discussion	Accounting books	Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Education	Explain the types of account	
9	35	Entrepreneurship and small business management	Recognize the role of entrepreneur and small business in the economy of Ghana	Meaning of entrepreneurship - Act of using personal initiative, engaging in calculated risk - taking ,to create new business venture by raising resources,, applying innovative and new ideas to develop product to serve problems for satisfaction	Explanation and Discussion	Economic books	Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Education	State 4 enterprise venture around you.	
10	70	Entrepreneurship and small business management	Acquire skills in establishing and growing small business in Ghana	Identify the role of entrepreneurs	Explanation And Discussion	Economics books	Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Education	State four roles of any business person in your society	

10	35	Entrepreneurship and small business management	Develop skills in using the principles learnt in solving problems through case study	Meaning of small business - Organization that is independently owned , financed and operated	Explanation and discussion	Economic books	Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). A Practical Approach to Doing Education	Define small businesses in your own words	
11	70	F I E L D T R I P							
11	35	C L A S S T E S T							
12	105	R E V I S I O N							
13	105	E X A M I N A T I O N							

CHAPTER THREE

TEACHING AND LEARNING RESOURCES

A. INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning resources is teacher and students support materials (TSM/SSM) that assist the teacher's/student work in the classroom. It is sometimes cumbersome to transfer new ideas and unknown information by making use of words, leading to the use of instructional materials that are visible and substantial.

B. IMPORTANCE OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS (TSM/SSM)

- They help to maintain the attention of students.
- Instructors / teachers do not only have to rely on their cognitive level
- They create so many venue and medium for delivering to communicate information.
- They develop differences in sensory impressions.
- Help teachers to replace real object if are unable to carry it to the classroom.

C. PLANNING TO USE INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN CLASSROOM

To ensure effective and efficiency in the classroom:

- Teachers must familiarize him/herself with the use and application of TSM and SSM.
- Teachers must also rehearse the presentation before going to the class in order to eschew the tendency of embarrassment when things do not go well.
- Teacher must do in-depth research and probing on the course and the environment in other to be on top of issues without any bias
- Teacher must allow student to make a feel of the materials only if it is hazardous.

D. TYPES OF TEACHING/LEARNING RESOURCES

For the purpose of this discussion, TSM/SSM can be grouped into two.

- Two dimensional, for examples, charts chalk board, pictures, overhead projectors (OPH) and transparencies instructional sheets etc.
- Three dimensional for example, models, real object.

E. TASK ANALYSIS

A task analysis is a logically related set of actions required for the completion of an entire piece of work.

A job consists of a number of tasks. To analyze the job, you have to list all the tasks that are involved the job.

a) Task Listing Sheet

Sheet is used to ensure that all important tasks in a programme of study are covered. A task listing sheet comprises of the following columns being: Number, Task and Frequency of performance, importance and learning challenges.

- **Number column:** The act of writing serial numbers of a task.
- **Task Column:** Contains the identified tasks of the vacation. The column also should contain only essential tasks.
- **Frequency of Performance:** In this column, how often the task identified is carried out in undertaking the job indicated the frequency column enables the teacher to plan and prepare for the tasks in time.
- **Importance Column:** The importance attached to the task. The tasks are graded from 1 to 5 to show their level of importance. A task graded 1 is important but grad 5 is the most important. The grading enables the teacher to handle those that are the most important so as they can be taught and learnt

even if it becomes extremely difficult to have time to teach and learn all tasks in a particular term or semester.

- **Learning difficulty Column:** Covers the difficulty level of the task. The task may be important but not difficult. The arrangement allows the teacher to spend more time and resources on the very difficult tasks. The difficulty level is graded from 1 to 5: 1 being easy and 5 being difficult.

b) Task Detailing Sheet

This is the second part of the task analysis process.

Task detailing sheet lists in order, the major steps involved in performing each of the tasks in the listing sheet.

Task detailing sheet also comprises of four columns, below:

- **Number Column:** Is the column where serial numbers of the tasks to be performed are listed.
- **Steps in Performing the Task:** This column lists the various steps required in performing the task logically.
- **Type of Performance:** This indicates the nature of performance. E.g. Recall, Manipulation, problem solving etc.
- **Learning Difficulty:** This column is graded from easy to very difficult.

F. INSTRUCTIONAL SHEETS

Instruction sheet is a group under instructional materials which are visible or written materials containing instructions to guide a student to perform a given task on a lesson.

There are four main types which are normally discussed. They are:

- Information sheet.
- Job sheet
- Operation sheet
- Assignment sheet

• INFORMATION SHEET

This is a written instructional material developed in the form of notes or handouts for a particular lesson.

➤ Characteristics of a good information sheet

- The information presented should be better understanding.
- Headings must be boldly written and underlined.
- The language used must be understood by the pupil.
- Paragraphs should be clearly separated from each other for easy reading.
- Sentences should be very short and brief for better comprehension.

SAMPLE INFORMATION SHEET

INSTITUTION	:	BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECHNICAL SCHOOL
SUBJECT	:	BUSINESS MANAGEMENT
TOPIC	:	NATURE OF MANAGEMENT
LESSON NO.	:	1
TERM	:	ONE

- a. Explaining the world of business
Evolution of man's effort to supply his or her needs since creation. Man has since time immemorial employed several ways in which to supply his needs and wants
- b. Explaining the concept of business organization
Entity involved in the transformation of resource into product and service in order to meet the needs of people.
- c. Identifying the major forms of business organization and their characteristics
 - Sole proprietorship
 - Partnership
 - Limited liability company
 - Public corporation
 - Co-operation
- d. Describing the procedures for the formation of various business organization
 - **Registration of Business Name** – According to Act 151, 1962 every company that is incorporated should be registered the name of the company in the registrar general department for name franchise and legitimacy
 - **Incorporation Partnership law** –Again with reference to Act 152 1962 , every company must be legally registered under the partnership law
 - **Company Code** – with regards to Act 179, 1963 , there should a document that contain the code of conduct and regulations that will guide companies

Describing the method for disturbing of profit and absorption of losses in various forms of business organization

- **Sole proprietor** – The owner take all profits and bears all losses
- **Partnership** – The partnership shares profit and losses in agreed ratios
- **Companies** – The profit are shared according to number of shares held by individual shareholders
- Outlining the causes of business failure
 - Managerial incompetence
 - Insufficient capital
 - Weak control system
 - Risk

REFERENCE: Fry.F.L. *Entrepreneurship: A planning Approach*. Eagan: west publishing .1993

SAMPLE INFORMATION SHEET

INSTITUTION	:	BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH TECHNICAL SCHOOL
SUBJECT	:	BUSINESS MANAGEMENT
TOPIC	:	MEANING AND PROCESS MANAGEMENT
LESSON NO.	:	2
TERM	:	ONE

a. Explaining the roles of the manager

Manager is someone who coordinate and oversees the work of other people in order to achieve organizational goals

- **Roles of Manager (Interpersonal)**

- Figurehead
- Leader
- Liaison

- **Informational**

- Monitor
- Disseminator
- Spokesperson

- **Decisional**

- Entrepreneur
- Disturbance handler
- Resource allocator
- Negotiator

- **Listing what make difference of how culture influence management practices in Ghana**

- Customs
- Belief
- Attitudes
- Values

b. Differencing administration from management

- **Administration** – It involves implementation of policies, procedures, regulations, rules, guidelines and sanctions
- **Management** – it is the concerned with policy formulation at the corporate level. The major roles or activities are planning, organizing, directing, and controlling monitoring, evaluation and feedback of organizational activities

- **Job Sheet**

Job sheet is a written list of instructions of the main steps arranged in order of performance for the completing an entire piece of work. This type of sheet is used when presenting a practical based oriented lesson.

- **Operation Sheet**

An operation sheet is a detailed written instruction describing exactly how to perform a given task systematically as listed in job sheet. It is gear towards aiding students to undergo systematic tasks after instruction exhibition.

- **Assignment Sheet**

An assignment sheet is used to assess and probe students study or performance of a procedures in project work undertaking.

SAMPLE ASSIGNMENT SHEET

NAME :	EBENEZER SIMONS -DADZIE	LESSON NO: 1
INSTITUTION:	BOMPEH SENIOR HIGH. TECH. SCH.	FORM: SHS ONE
DEPARTMENT:	BUSINESS	TERM: ONE
SUBJECT :	BUSINESS MANAGEMENT	

QUESTIONS

1. Explain the concept of business
2. Identify the major form of organization in Ghana
3. State and explain the characteristics of forms of business
4. Describe the procedures in formation of business in Ghana
5. Outline the causes of business failure in Ghana

SUBMISSION DATE: AUGUST 20TH 2021

LESSON PLAN

- Introduction

A lesson plan is an instructional guide that shows how resources (both human and physics) will be organized so that students will acquire and develop the expected knowledge and skills, the lesson plan is more detailed than scheme of work and it is prepared in a specific lesson

- Reasons for preparing and using a lesson plan

Teacher plan their lesson because of the following reasons:

1. The lesson plan enables the teacher instructor to present his or her lesson logically
2. It enables all the instructional objectives to be achieved.
3. Appropriate instructional materials (e.g assignment, exercise, projects) can be identified and given to pupils / students.
4. The lesson plan serves as a record of work done so that topics are not necessarily repeated.
5. The lesson plan serves as a record of work done so that topics are not necessarily repeated.
6. The teacher / instructor can prepare test items using the instructional objectives formulated in the lesson plan.
7. It enables the teacher/instructor to work within the stipulated time.

- Factors to Consider When Planning A Lesson

The main issues to consider when planning a lesson are the following:

- i. Topics: considers whether the topics selected for the lesson is taken form the scheme of work or syllabus.
- ii. Expected learning outcomes: the instructional objectives will clearly state the content of the lesson topics so that end of the lesson, behavior changes can be measured.
- iii. Instructional materials: In order to teach with only suitable materials, both the teacher and student / learner support materials can be identified and be made clearly.
- iv. Time/duration: the period of time must be considered so that the rate of delay can be controlled.
- v. Classroom / workshop place: the place where the lesson will be presented must be known and made ready.
- vi. Activities to be assigned: for a successful evaluation of the lesson, learners activities (i.e class exercises, project work and assignment should be added in the lesson)

- Stages in Lesson Preparation

The four main stages in lesson preparation are the

1. Preparation stage
2. Presentation stage
3. Application stage
4. Testing stage

These stages must link each other

a. Preparation Stage

At this stage, the following must be considered;

1. Formation of general and specific objectives
2. Selection of the appropriate teaching and learning strategies
3. Identification and selection of instructional materials (both teachers and learners support materials)
4. The selection of appropriate activities (e.g exercise, project and test)
5. Selection of the subject matter.

b. Presentation Stage

This is the stage that a teacher actually delivers his or her lesson after preparation.

The presentation must involve the following.

1. Introduction of the lesson by means of question, stories etc
2. Using varied methods of presentation (e.g lecture, discussion, demonstration)
3. Linking all new material, factors and procedure to those already taught.
- c. Application stage

This stage encourages the students to practice or try out their ability or level of understanding on the things they have been taught. At this stage, the teacher should consider when the following:

1. Giving relevant exercise or project
2. Ensuring that all the students participate in the activities.
- d. The testing stage assists both the teacher and student to find out whether the stated instructional objectives have been achieved. The student is required to demonstrate his or her ability or competency with no help from the teacher. The stage helps the teacher and the student to:
 1. Evaluate the effect of the teaching and learning activities
 2. Determine strength and weaknesses
 3. Determine whether the student should be promoted or not.

LESSON PLAN FORMAT

NAME :	LESSON NO.:
INSTITUTION:	FORM:
DEPARTMENT:	DURATION:
SUBJECT :	DATE:
TOPIC:	

INSTRUCTIONAL OBJECTIVES

By the end of the lesson students will be able to:

GENERAL OBJECTIVES	1.0
SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	1.1

REFERENCE**TEACHING / LEARNING RESOURCES**

1. Teacher Support Materials (T.S.M)
2. Student support Material (S.S.M)

PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT

CONTENT BREAKDOWN KEY POINTS	METHODOLOGY		TIME (MINS)
	TEACHER ACTIVITY	STUDENT ACTIVITY	
INTRODUCTION			
STEP 1			
STEP 2			
STEP 3			
APPLICATION			
CONCLUSION			

ASSIGNMENT:**REMARKS:****SAMPLE OF LESSON PLAN**

NAME: EBENEZER SIMONS –DADZIE FORM. SHS ONE
 INSTITUTION: BOMPEH SEN. HIGH.TECH.SCH DURATION: 1HR
 DEPARTMENT: BUSINESS LESSON NO.: 1
 SUBJECT: BUSINESS MANAGEMENT DATE: 10/07/2021

INSTRUCTIONAL OBJECTIVE: By the end of the lesson the student will be able to:

- 1.0. Define small scale businesses in their words with examples
- 1.1. State the importance of small scale businesses and how to fund it .
- 1.2. Mention four ways to ensure sustainability of small scale businesses
- 1.3. Outline four challenges / problems facing small scale businesses
- 1.4. State and explain four roles of government to support small scale businesses

REFER ENCE: Fry.F.L. Entrepreneurship: A planning Approach. Eagan: west publishing .1993

TEACHING / LEARNING RESOURCES

Teacher Support Material (TSM): Pictures, Business management textbook, handouts and information sheet

Student Support Material (SSM): Pictures, Business management textbook, handouts and information sheet.

Relevant Previous Knowledge: Student shared their idea on small scale businesses

DEVELOPMENT

CONTENT BREAKDOWN KEY POINTS	METHODOLOGY		TIME (MINS)
	TEACHER ACTIVITY	STUDENT ACTIVITY	
INTRODUCTION	Teacher ask questions to bring out the topic	Students answers the question to bring out the topic and write the topic on the board	5
STEP 1. Definition of small scale businesses with example	Teacher ask question , guide students to define small scale business with examples into their note books	Students write the standard definition in their note books	5
STEP 2.Mention four ways to ensure sustainability of small scale businesses	Teacher ask question ,assist students to mention four ways to ensure sustainability of small scale businesses	Students write the ways in their note books	20
STEP 3.Outline four challenges / problems facing small scale businesses	Teacher ask question, help students to outline the challenges and problem facing small scale business	Students write the challenges and problems facing small scale businesses in their note	15
STEP 4.State and explain four roles of government to support small scale businesses	Teacher help students to explain the role of government in supporting small scale business	Students write the roles of government in their note books	15
APPLICATION. 1. Definition of small scale businesses with example 2.Mention four ways to ensure sustainability of small scale businesses 3..Outline four challenges / problems facing small scale businesses 4.State and explain four roles of government to support small scale business	Teacher write question on board to ask students to answer in their note books and then go around to check their answer	Students answer question in their own words	7
CONCLUSION	Teacher answer question from the students	Students ask question	3

ASSIGNMENT

1. Do you think society has a roles to play in sustaining small scale businesses? Yes/ No. Explain your reason.

REMARKS: The lesson objective% achieved

CHAPTER FOUR

TEST ITEMS CONSTRUCTION

A. INTRODUCTION

This is the process of determining the level of understanding or performance of a student in a particular subject or skills. It also necessary for the teacher to assess the progress of students learning and this may be then in a systematic procedure.

There are many forms of test, each serving a purpose at different occasions. This may either be a subjective form or objective form.

- **SUBJECTIVE TEST:** This is prepared in a way that the responses involved lengthy written example, description, discussion, illustration and explanation.
- **OBJECTIVE TEST:** These are prepared in a way that the scoring procedure is always objective. This type of tests of two types. Namely, the supply type and selection response type, test item must be limited to the objectives.

B. TEST ITEMS CONSTRUCTION

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C. THE TABLE OF SPECIFICATION

This is planning document, which contains the format on which any kind of achievement test may be planned. This may be produced on one test. Examples (written objectives practical, project work, oral and so on and this have two major dimensions normally abilities and topic

a) Topic

This contains the unit of the subject that will be the basic of the test. This list of topics selected to be tested. Questions are set to be covered several aspect of the topic to be tested. The total number of question to be clearly answered should also be written at the bottom right hand corner of the table, the total of this should represent the relative importance on each topic.

b) Abilities

This contains the aspect of the overall ability tested. It may consist of different aspect.

The ability or recall (memory) rehabilitates may range in ability such as knowledge comprehension and application.

TABLE OF SPECIFICATION**OBJECTIVE TEST**

TOPICS	LEARNING OUTCOMES						TOTAL
	KNOWLEDGE	COMPREHENSION	APPLICATION	ANALYSIS	SYNTHESIS	EVALUATION	
Planning	2	3	-	-	-	-	5
Decision making	2	3	1	-	-	-	6
Organizing	3	3	2	-	-	-	8
Delegation	2	3	1	-	-	-	6
Communication	3	2	2	1	-	-	8
Monitoring and Controlling	2	2	1	1	-	1	7
Law of Contract	3	2	-	-	-	-	5
Total	-	-	-	-	-	-	45

TABLE OF SPECIFICATION**ESSAY TEST**

TOPICS	LEARNING OUTCOMES						TOTAL
	KNOWLEDGE	COMPREHENSION	APPLICATION	ANALYSIS	SYNTHESIS	EVALUATION	
Law of contract	3	2	3	-	-	-	
Communication	2	2	1	-	-	-	5
Forms of business organization	5	4	1	2	-	-	12
Business and society	3	1	1	1	-	-	6
Monitoring and Controlling	1	2	-	-	-	-	3
Integrating information and communication Technologies	-	2	1	-	-	-	3
Information search skills	-	3	-	-	-	-	3
Legal framework of business	2	1	1	-	-	-	4
Financial and Non- Financial institution	3	2	1	1	-	-	7
Total	-	-	-	-	-	-	45

D. TEST ITEMS

The test items are written statements which require respondent to demonstrate essential knowledge or skills.

a) TYPES OF TEST ITEM

Basically there are two main types of test item. These are:

- Essay test items
- Objective test items

b) ESSAY TEST ITEMS

This is a type of test which requires students to:

- Compose his or her own response.
- The response is usually in the form of one or more sentences.
- No single response can be said to be entirely correct or wrong.
- The response could only be judged or scored by a well-informed-person or examiner in the area.

c) TYPES OF ESSAY

- Restricted response / close ended response
- Extended / open ended response

d) GUIDELINES FOR CONSTRUCTION ESSAY TEST

- Plan the test.
- Restrict the use of essay test to measure the higher order domain eg. Synthesis, evaluation, etc
- Use a relatively large number of restricted response which requires short answers.
- Options must be avoided in essay test to a great extent.
- There should not be too much ambiguities.

e) FACTORS TO CONSIDER WHEN PLANNING AN ESSAY TEST

- Availability of time.
- The size of the class.
- Whether the teacher is a prolific reader or not (someone who is good at reading and scoring marks.)
- Question optionality.

f) FACTORS AFFECTING SCORING OF ESSAY TEST

- Handwriting
- Gender
- Language / Grammar
- Student appearance (halo effect)
- Ethnicity
- The size of the class
- The length of the response
- Teacher's mood
- The syllabus covered
- The population of the class

g) HOW TO REDUCE SUBJECTIVITY IN SCORING ESSAY TEST

- Use index numbers of students instead of names.
- Be in stable condition when scoring or marking.
- Use multiple examiners
- Prepare a comprehensive scoring scheme
- Score seriating (i.e. item by item)
- Score content not grammar or hand writing etc

h) OBJECTIVE TEST ITEM

A test which provides an opportunity to determine the best or correct answer that is, subjective opinion in scoring, is eliminated. An objective test is objective because of scoring. Its objectivity is the effectiveness by which one can determine the correct answer.

i) TYPES OF OBJECTIVE TEST

The main types of objective tests are:

- Multiple choice type
- Matching type
- True and false (Yes or No) type
- Supply type.

E. SAMPLE TEST ITEMS - OBJECTIVES**1. SECTION 'A'****2. CHOOSE THE CORRECT ANSWER FROM THE GIVEN OPTIONS****3. LETTERED A-D TO ANSWER THE QUESTION BELOW**

1. The document which serves as evidence for the registration of a company is
 - (a) Articles of Association.
 - (b) Certificate of Incorporation.
 - (c) Certificate of Trading.
 - (d) Memorandum Of Association
2. Which Of The Following Activities Comes First In A Business Decision-Making Process?
 - A. Identifying The Problem
 - B. Gathering Of Information
 - C. Developing Alternatives
 - D. Making A Choice
3. The Sets Of Programs Which Instruct A Computer How To Do A Particular Job Is
 - A. Database
 - B. Hardware
 - C. Memory
 - D. Software
4. The Means Of Exchanging Goods For Goods In International Trade Is
 - A. Barter Trade.
 - B. Counter Trade.
 - C. Entrepot Trade.
 - D. Terms of Trade.
5. The Salaries Paid To Government Employees Are Classified Under
 - A. Balance of Payment.
 - B. Capital Account.
 - C. Capital Expenditure.
 - D. Recurrent Expenditure.
6. A Woman Who Smoke Fish For Sale Is Engaged In
 - A. Direct Service.
 - B. Extractive Industry.
 - C. Indirect Service.
 - D. Manufacturing Industry.
7. The Channel Through Which Policies Are Communicated To Employees Of An Organization Is
 - A. Diagonal Communication.
 - B. Downward Communication.
 - C. Horizontal Communication.
 - D. Upward Communication
8. The Elements Of The Marketing Mix Are
 - A. Promotion, Advertising, Sales and Distribution.
 - B. Production, Procurement, Sales and Pricing.
 - C. Pricing, Production, Personnel and Purchasing.
 - D. Product, Price, Promotion and Place.
9. A Refund By Customs Authority To An Importer For Duty Already Paid On Goods Re-Exported Is
 - A. Customs Drawback.
 - B. Excise Duty.
 - C. Import Duty.
 - D. Sales Tax.

10. The Document Of Title To Be Presented To Clear Goods At The Port Is
 - A. Bill Of Lading.
 - B. Certificate of Inspection.
 - C. Certificate of Origin.
 - D. Consular Invoice.
11. In A Partnership, The Bankruptcy Of A Partner Would Lead To It's
 - A. Continuity
 - B. Incorporation
 - C. Liquidation
 - D. Solvency
12. An Advantage Of Product Branding To An Organization Is The
 - A. Differentiation of Items from Similar Products.
 - B. Increased Competition From Other Brands.
 - C. Increased Volume Of Production.
 - D. Reduction inthe Cost of Production.
13. The End Point Towards Which All Organizations' Efforts Are Directed Is
 - A. Objective
 - B. Policy
 - C. Rule
 - D. Strategy
14. Which Of The Following Activities Is Part Of An Organizing Function Of Management
 - A. Analyzing The Reasons For Deviations
 - B. Determining The Span Of Control
 - C. Formulating Objectives And Strategies
 - D. Providing Motivation For Employees
15. A Step In Production Planning Which Gives A Timetable For The Commencement And Completion Of A Job Is
 - A. Dispatching
 - B. Loading
 - C. Routing
 - D. Scheduling
16. A Contract Under Which A Party Undertakes To Indemnify Another Against A Risk Is
 - A. Assurance
 - B. Insurance
 - C. Partnership Deed.
 - D. Sale of Goods.
17. Commercial Banks Lend Money To Individuals And Firms In The Form Of
 - A. Interest and Profits.
 - B. Loans and Overdrafts.
 - C. Shares and Loans.
18. An Objective Of The Labor Union Is To
 - A. The Salary Of Its Members.
 - B. Organize Strikes When There Is Misunderstanding.
 - C. Rally Active Workers against Government.
 - D. Work towards Better Conditions for Its Members.
19. The Use Of One Cheque To Pay A Number Of People Through A Commercial Bank Is
 - A. Credit Transfer.
 - B. Direct Debit.
 - C. Payment Order.
 - D. Standing Order.

20. A current account holder is eligible for which of the following services
 - A. Interest-free loan
 - B. Leasing facility
 - C. Overdraft facility
 - D. use of savings withdrawal form
21. The Profits Of A Public Corporation Belong, To The
 - A. Board of Directors.
 - B. Debenture Holders.
 - C. Government
 - D. Shareholders
22. In Decision-Making Process, The Step That Determines The Scope And Use Of Resources To Solve The Problem Falls Under
 - A. Analysis ofthe Problem.
 - B. Gathering Of Information.
 - C. Development of Alternatives.
 - D. Evaluation of Alternatives.
23. An Organizational Chart Depicts
 - A. Channels of Informal Communication.
 - B. The Number of Customers.
 - C. The Number of Employees.
 - D. The Structure ofan Organization.
24. An Element In The Law Of Contract Is That
 - A. Acceptance Must Be Communicated.
 - B. All Agreements Must Be Sealed.
 - C. An Offer Must Be Moved By A Promisee.
 - D. Principals Should Always Ratify Agents' Acts.
25. The Distribution Function Of Marketing Involves
 - A. Product Development and Packaging.
 - B. Production Facilities and Employee Welfare.
 - C. Segmentation and Pricing Policy.
 - D. Transportation and Warehousing.
26. The Type Of Training Which Seeks To Provide Employees With Work Experience In All Areas Of The Company's Operation Is
 - A. Apprenticeship
 - B. Coaching
 - C. Job Rotation.
 - D. Understudy Assignment.
27. In A Contract, An Agreement Is Reached When An
 - A. Offeror Gives Consideration.
 - B. Offeror Gives A Promise.
 - C. Offeree Accepts The Offer.
 - D. Offeree Declines The Offer.
28. A Reason For Job Interview Is To
 - A. Assess The Suitability Of Applicants.
 - B. Check The Health Status Of The Applicants.
 - C. Give The Applicant opportunity to introduce referees.
 - D. Revise information given on the application form.

29. When the amount in words and figures differ on a cheque presented by a third party, the drawee will
 - A. Ask the payee to make the necessary correction.
 - B. Ask the payee to destroy the cheque.
 - C. Dishonor and return the cheque to the drawer.
 - D. Pay the higher amount to the payee.
30. Goods which consumers buy frequently in small quantities with less effort are
 - A. Assorted goods.
 - B. Capital goods.
 - C. Convenience goods.
 - D. Specialty goods.
31. Marketing begins with the
 - A. Selection of channels of distribution.
 - B. Pricing of a product.
 - C. Development of the product.
 - D. Conception of the product.
32. An advice note is issued by a seller to a buyer to inform him of the
 - A. Amount due for payment.
 - B. Arrival date of goods ordered.
 - C. Available goods and terms of payment.
 - D. Intention not to sell goods to him.
33. The use of computers in a business is influenced by
 - A. Legal factor.
 - B. Political factor.
 - C. Social factor.
 - D. Technological factor.
34. The role of government in an economy is to
 - A. Create enabling environment for businesses.
 - B. Discourage foreign investments.
 - C. Encourage foreign competition.
 - D. Generate revenue for government officials.
35. When workers refuse to complete their tasks as a way of protest, this action is a form of
 - A. boycott
 - B. lobby
 - C. picketing
 - D. Work-to-rule.
36. A document issued by a seller to a buyer to inform him of his present indebtedness and the need to pay is
 - A. Credit note.
 - B. Debit note.
 - C. Preform invoice.
 - D. Statement of accounts.
37. A sole proprietorship form of business changes to a partnership when
 - A. it acquires more capital and resources.
 - B. it employs more qualified workers.
 - C. it opens branches nationwide.
 - D. the number of its owners increases.
38. Which of the following books will a business operator use to record smaller expenses
 - A. Cash book
 - B. Petty cash book
 - C. Purchases day book
 - D. Sales day book

39. The qualifications that a prospective employee must possess are contained in the job
- A. enlargement
 - B. description
 - C. enrichment
 - D. specification
40. Lender of last resort is a function performed by the
- A. Central bank.
 - B. Commercial bank.
 - C. Community bank.
 - D. Co-operative bank.

F. SECTION B – ESSAY TEST

ANSWER ALL THE QUESTIONS BELOW

- 1(a) State four functions of a commercial bank
(b) List two techniques in time management
- 2(a) Explain the term trade union
(b) Outline five functions of a trade union
(c) Explain five reasons for workers going on strike
- 3(a) what is organizing as it relates to management function?
(b) Explain all the functions of management

G. MARKING SCHEME

The marking scheme is an outline of the score indicating which mark will be allocated to what question. It is also known as the scoring scheme.

a) **TYPES OF MARKING SCHEME FOR ESSAY**

Generally, there are two types of marking scheme. They are:

b) **Analytical point method**

In this type of scheme, the examiner looks for specific points for which to award the marks.

c) **Global or impression method**

The examiner reads the script and scores according to the influence on him / her or ability to convince the examiner.

OBJECTIVE TEST FOR MARKING SCHEME

Question Number	Answer	Question Number	Answer
1	B	16	B
2	A	17	C
3	D	18	D
4	C	19	C
5	D	20	C
6	D	21	C
7	D	22	D
8	D	23	D
9	D	24	A
10	A	25	D
11	A	26	C
12	A	27	C
13	A	28	A
14	B	29	C
15	D	30	C
		31	D
		32	B
		33	D
		34	A
		35	D
		36	D
		37	D
		38	B
		39	D
		40	A
TOTAL	40 MARKS		

ESSAY TEST – SECTION ‘B’ MARKING SCHEME

QUESTION NUMBER	NUMBER OF POINTS (ANSWER) DEMANDED	MARKS	TOTAL
1. a b	Good explanation	10	20
		10	
2. a b c	Good explanation	7	20
		11	
		2	
3. a b	Good explanation	10	20
		10	

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. SUMMARY

This research was written to draw the attention of both teachers and students about effective utilization of the Teaching Syllabus, Lesson Order, Scheme of Work, Lesson Plan as well as Teaching and Learning Resources in the teaching of business management in senior secondary schools in Ghana.

B. CONCLUSION

The rational of some people is that anybody and everybody can teach must be rejected because, teaching is an art and follows many pedagogical methodology in delivery. Teaching profession is a noble and reputable and must be seen as such by everybody. The situation where teaching was solely seen as an art is past and gone. It therefore needs a strategic planning and systematic arrangement of all resources needed for facilitating and assisting the acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitude in the area of business management.

C. RECOMMENDATIONS

I recommend that the current syllabus must be amended to suit the current world of highly technological and industrial advancement competition for their students to live to standard of international recognition.

Again, after the research, I recommend that when implementing syllabus, there should be an affective interactions with teachers, community's leaders and other stakeholders to gather some ideas that can add positive progress in their respective society.

Moreover, I also recommend that the syllabus must be practical base- oriented for the students to get hands on practical skills.

Finally, I recommend that the syllabus must help the teachers to deliver teaching and learning that will provoke the student inquisitorial minds by covering the domains of education (psychomotor, cognitive and affective).

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adentwi, K.I, Amartey, M.A. (2012). *A Practical Approach to Doing Educational Research* Kumasi: Ebens Printing Press
- [2.] ANECA. (2005). *Business management and administration degree white book*. Retrieved from libroblanco economy. ANECA. (2006).
- [3.] Armengol, C. (2004). *A frame for the elaboration of formation programs adapted to the European credit philosophy*. Communication of the III International Congress “University learning and Innovation”, April, 2008, <http://www.upf.edu/bolonya/butlletins/2005/febrer1/marc.pdf>.
- [4.] CR DOCENTIA. *Backup program for the evaluation of the teaching activity of the university teaching staff*. Evaluation’s models..
- [5.] DD (2007) *Teaching Syllabus for business management (S.H.S.)*
- [6.] De Miguel, M. (2004). *Adaptation from the study programs to the process of European convergence*. Education and Science Ministry. (Ed.).
- [7.] De Miguel, M. and other ones. (2006). *Teaching and learning methodologies for the development of competencies: Orientations for the university teaching staff for the European Higher Education Area*. Editorial Alliance Corporation,
- [8.] Gonzalez, J. & Wagenaar, R. (2003). *Educational structures, learning outcomes, workload and the calculation of ECTS credits*, in tuning educational structures in Europe. Final report phase one.
- [9.] Gonzalez, J. & Wagenaar, R. (2006). *The tuning management committee introduction to tuning educational structures in Europe II*. Retrieved March, 2008, from <http://tuning.unideusto.org/tuningeu/images/stories/template/General> Brochure Spanish April, 2008,
- [10.] Jaume I University Castellón (Spain). (2006). *Guidebook to elaborate educational teaching guides, ECTS*
- [11.] Madrid. European Commission. (2006). *The extent and impact of higher education curricular reform across Europe..*